

FIRST-APPROXIMATION GEOMETRICALLY NONLINEAR
COMPOSITE SHELL THEORY

I.F. Obraztsov and V.V. Vasil'ev
Moscow Institute of Aviation Technology
Moscow, 103767
USSR

ABSTRACT

A constrained first approximation geometrically nonlinear theory of thin composite shells based on nonlinear equations of three-dimensional theory of elasticity, overaging of transverse shear strains and stresses over the shell thickness, and disregard of the thickness stretching is discussed. Being derived for composite shells undergoing only small deflections (for many engineering problems it is hardly necessary to allow large deformations), governing equations of the theory under consideration have the simplest nonlinear form and describe the most essential nonlinear effects attributed to the changes of shell curvature under loading. The corresponding boundary conditions obtained by variational approach and nonlinear equations of the membrane shell theory are also presented. A simple iterative technique available for the solution of the derived nonlinear equations is described. Results of analysis for composite cylindrical shells considered as examples demonstrate essential influence of nonlinear effects on shells behavior and fair agreement with the exact solution and experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

As it is known, there exists a number of geometrically nonlinear shell theories based on various assumptions about the order of magnitude of strains and rotations of a shell element. If strains and rotations (or displacements and

the corresponding gradients) can be regarded as relatively small, shell behavior is usually described by linear equations. However, in composite shells which are characterized by high membrane strength and relatively low bending stiffness small strains and rotations can be accompanied by large derivatives of rotations inducing essential changes of shell curvature. Consider for example a thin ($h/R = 0.02$) hemispherical clamped composite shell loaded with internal pressure (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Deformation of a hemispherical shell.

As one can see in Fig.1, the strain ($\Delta R/R$) and the rotation (θ) are small in comparison with unity ($\Delta R/R \leq 0.01$, $\theta \leq 0.07$), however, the change of the meridional curvature (ξ) exceeds considerably its initial value $1/R$ (i.e. $R\xi \leq 2$) and should be taken into account.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Let us consider an element of the laminated shell shown in Fig.2 and referred to the orthogonal curvilinear coordinates x_1, x_2, x_3 . To obtain governing equations of the discussed composite shell theory nonlinear equations of three-dimensional elasticity [1] and a set of simplifying assumptions will be used. Assuming that strains and

Figure 2. An element of the composite shell.

rotations are small in comparison with unity one can employ linear strain-displacement relations. Averaging transverse shear strains over the thickness of the shell [2]

$$f_1(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-e}^{h-e} e_{13} dx_3 \quad (1,2) \quad (1)$$

neglecting transverse normal strain and adopting that the radius-to-thickness ratio is large one can obtain the following geometrical relations of the shell theory

$$e_{11} = e_1 + x_3 k_1 \quad (1,2) \quad e_{12} = e_3 + x_3 k_3 \quad (2)$$

where

$$e_1 = \frac{u_{1,1}}{A_1} + \frac{u_2}{A_1 A_2} A_{1,2} + \frac{w}{R_1}, \quad k_1 = \frac{\theta_{1,1}}{A_1} + \frac{\theta_2}{A_1 A_2} A_{1,2} \quad (1,2)$$

$$e_3 = \frac{u_{2,1}}{A_1} + \frac{u_{1,2}}{A_2} - \frac{1}{A_1 A_2} (u_1 A_{1,2} + u_2 A_{2,1}) \quad (3)$$

$$k_3 = \frac{2_{,1}}{A_1} + \frac{1_{,2}}{A_2} - \frac{1}{A_1 A_2} (\theta_1 A_{1,2} + \theta_2 A_{2,1})$$

$$\theta_1 = f_1 + v_1, \quad v_1 = (u_1/R_1) - (w_{,1}/A_1)$$

in which u_1, u_2 and w are displacements of the reference surface, A_1 and R_1 are the coefficients of the first fundamental quadratic form and principal radii of curvature

of the reference surface, respectively. The indices 1,2 after commas denote differentiation with respect to x_1, x_2 . The notation (1,2) in Eq.(1) and further means that the analogous equation with 1 and 2 interchanged is also applicable.

The strains e_1, e_2, e_{12} are expressed by means of Eqs.2 through eight two-dimensional functions (3) $e(x_1, x_2), k(x_1, x_2)$ and $f(x_1, x_2)$. Let us introduce the corresponding stress resultants and couples. The stress-strain relations for the orthotropic material are given by

$$\sigma_1 = A_{11}e_{11} + A_{12}e_{22} \quad (1,2) \quad \tau_{12} = A_{33}e_{12} \quad (4)$$

According to Eqs. (2),(4) one can write the following constitutive relations which are consistent with the geometrical equations (2)

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} N_1 \\ M_1 \end{bmatrix} &= \int_{-e}^{h-e} \sigma_1 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} dx_3 = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}e_1 + B_{12}e_2 + C_{11}k_1 + C_{12}k_2 \\ C_{11}e_1 + C_{12}e_2 + D_{11}k_1 + D_{12}k_2 \end{bmatrix} (1,2) \\ \begin{bmatrix} N_3 \\ M_3 \end{bmatrix} &= \int_{-e}^{h-e} \tau_{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} dx_3 = \begin{bmatrix} B_{33}e_3 + C_{33}k_3 \\ C_{33}e_3 + D_{33}k_3 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Membrane or stretching (B_{mn}), bending-stretching coupling (C_{mn}), and bending (D_{mn}) stiffnesses have the form

$$\begin{aligned} B_{mn} &= I_{mn}^{(0)}, \quad C_{mn} = I_{mn}^{(1)} - eI_{mn}^{(0)} \\ D_{mn} &= I_{mn}^{(2)} - 2eI_{mn}^{(1)} + e^2I_{mn}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where for the shell composed of a finite number (k) of orthotropic layers

$$I_{mn}^{(r)} = \int_0^h A_{mn} t^{(r)} dt = \frac{1}{r+1} \sum_{i=1}^k A_{mn}^{(i)} (t_i^{r+1} - t_{i-1}^{r+1})$$

in which $r = 0, 1, 2$ and $t = e + x_3$ (Fig.2). In general case Eqs.(6) take the simplest form if the reference surface coincides with the bottom surface of the shell (i.e. if $e=0$). For the shell which structure is symmetric about the midsurface one can eliminate bending-stretching stiffnesses in Eqs.(5) by setting $e = h/2$.

Let us obtain now constitutive relations for transverse shear stress resultants

$$Q_1 = \int_{-e}^{h-e} \tau_{13} dx_3 \quad (1,2)$$

Substitution of

$$e_{13} = \tau_{13}/G_{13} \quad (1,2) \quad (7)$$

into Eq.(1) yields

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-e}^{h-e} \frac{\tau_{13}}{G_{13}} dx_3 \quad (1,2) \quad (8)$$

Note that f_1 is the transverse shear deformation averaged over the thickness of the shell. Equation (7) shows that it is quite natural to average the corresponding shear stress by setting $\tau_{13} = Q_1/h$ in Eq.(8). The result has the form

$$Q_1 = K_1 f_1 \quad (1,2) \quad (9)$$

where for the laminated shell

$$K_1 = h^2 \left(\int_{-e}^{h-e} dx_3 / G_{13} \right)^{-1} = h^2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^k (t_i - t_{i-1}) / G_{13}^{(i)} \right]^{-1}$$

Consider the equilibrium equations. Initial nonlinear three-dimensional elasticity equations can be reduced in a traditional manner (multiplication by 1 and x_3 and integration over the thickness of the shell) to two-dimensional shell theory equations which can be further simplified within the assumptions made previously. According to these assumptions let us neglect all nonlinear terms except those including the derivatives of rotations. Moreover, nonlinear terms which contain shear stress resultants Q_1, Q_2 are also neglected for they are significant, as some additional analysis shows, only for beams and thick plates. The result is as follows

$$L_1(N) + (A_1 A_2 / R_1) Q_1 + A_1 A_2 t_1 = 0 \quad (1,2)$$

$$(A_2 Q_1)_{,1} + (A_1 Q_2)_{,2} - (A_1 A_2 / R_1) N_1 - (A_1 A_2 / R_2) N_2 \quad (10)$$

$$-N_1 A_2 v_{1,1} - N_3 (A_2 v_{2,1} + A_1 v_{1,2}) - N_2 A_1 v_{2,2} + A_1 A_2 t_3 = 0$$

$$L_1(M) - A_1 A_2 Q_1 + A_1 A_2 m_1 = 0 \quad (1,2)$$

where

$$L(F) = (A_2 F_1)_{,1} - F_2 A_{2,1} + (A_1 F_3)_{,2} + F_3 A_{1,2} \quad (1,2)$$

$$t_1 = \int_{-e}^{h-e} X_1 dx_3 + p_1 + q_1 \quad (1,2), \quad t_3 = \int_{-e}^{h-e} X_3 dx_3 + p - q$$

$$m_1 = \int_{-e}^{h-e} X_1 x_3 dx_3 + (h-e)q_1 - ep_1 \quad (1,2)$$

in which $F = (N; M)$, X_i are body forces, p and q are surface loads shown in Fig.2.

Thus the obtained set includes equations (3),(5),(9), (10) and has the 10-th order with respect to x_1 and x_2 . Variational formulation of the problem allows one to derive the following natural boundary conditions (e.g. along the edge $x_1 = \text{const}$)

$$N_1 \delta u_1 = 0, \quad M_1 \delta \theta_1 = 0, \quad N_3 \delta u_2 = 0, \quad M_3 \delta \theta_2 = 0$$

$$(Q_1 - N_1 v_1 - N_3 v_2) \delta w = 0$$

The obtained equations differ from those corresponding to the linear shell theory only by the form of the second equilibrium equation (10) which includes the products of the membrane stress resultants and the changes of the curvature of the shell reference surface. To solve these equations a simple iterative technique which reduces them to a set of linear equations can be employed. According to this procedure the initial iteration corresponds to the linear solution and at the n -th iteration the membrane stress resultants in the nonlinear terms are preassigned as a result obtained at the previous $(n-1)$ -th iteration. The convergence of this process is illustrated in Fig.3 which shows the dependence of the axial displacement of the loaded polar opening of a filament wound isotensoid pressure vessel [3] upon the number of iteration n .

Consider a membrane shell undertaking only stress resultants N_1, N_2, N_3 . By setting $C_{mn} = D_{mn} = 0$ in Eqs.(10) one can obtain the following governing equations of the nonlinear membrane shell theory

$$L_1(N) + A_1 A_2 t_1 = 0 \quad (1,2)$$

$$\frac{N_1}{R_1} + \frac{N_2}{R_2} + \frac{N_1}{A_1} v_{1,1} + N_3 \left(\frac{v_{2,1}}{A_1} + \frac{v_{1,2}}{A_2} \right) + \frac{N_2}{A_2} v_{2,2} = t_3$$

the corresponding constitutive equations

$$N_1 = B_{11}e_1 + B_{12}e_2 \quad (1,2), \quad N_3 = B_{33}e_3$$

and the boundary conditions

$$N_1 \delta u_1 = 0, \quad N_3 \delta u_2 = 0, \quad (N_1 v_1 + N_3 v_2) \delta w = 0$$

The obtained set of equations has the 6-th order and in contrast to linear membrane shell theory equations allows to find the solution which is continuous up to the boundaries with respect to all components of displacement.

Figure 3. Variation of displacement u with the number of iteration.

EXAMPLES

As examples let us consider two one-dimensional problems for which closed-form solutions are readily obtained.

First consider an infinitely long shallow composite cylindrical panel clamped along the straight edges and loaded with internal pressure (Fig.4). Neglecting transverse shear strains one can write

$$N_2' = 0, \quad M_2' - Q_2 = 0, \quad Q_2' - N_2 \left(\frac{1}{R} - w'' \right) + p = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$N_2 = B(u_2' + \frac{w}{R}), \quad M_2 = -Dw''$$

In Eqs.(11) prime denotes differentiation with respect to x_2 and the coordinate of the reference surface (e) was found from the condition $C_{22} = 0$.

Figure 4. Deflection of the panel.

Taking into account the boundary conditions $u_2(-b)=u_2(b)=0$ one can reduce Eqs.(11) to the following

$$N_2 = N, \quad w'''' - mw'' = \frac{p}{D}(1 - n), \quad N = \frac{B}{Rb} \int_0^b w dx_2$$

where $m=N/D$, $n=N/pR$. For a cross-ply laminated panel with $h/R=1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $b/R=0.075$, $B=0.278$ Gpa.m, $D=0.134 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Gpa.m³, $p=0.1$ Mpa the solution is shown in Fig.4 by curve 1 ($w_0=pR^2/B$). Curve 2 corresponds to the linear solution ($m=0$), curve 3 - to the nonlinear membrane equations ($D=0$), and circles indicate the nonlinear solution [4] based on Von-Karman type equations. Note that the deflection of the panel is less than its thickness. Nevertheless, the nonlinear solution is closer to the membrane than to the linear one.

As the second example consider an axisymmetrical problem for a composite cylindrical shell loaded with internal pressure and reinforced by a steel ring (Fig.5). In this case

governing equations have the form

$$N_1' = 0, \quad M_1' - Q_1 = 0, \quad Q_1' + N_1 w'' - (N_2/R) + p = 0$$

$$N_1 = B_{11} u_1' + B_{12} (w/R), \quad M_1 = C_{12} (w/R) + D (f_1' - w'')$$

$$N_2 = B_{21} u_1' + B_{22} (w/R) + C_{12} (f_1' - w''), \quad Q_1 = K_1 f_1'$$

where prime denotes differentiation with respect to x_1 and coordinate e was found from the condition $C_{11} = 0$.

Figure 5. Cylindrical shell with a ring and its deflection under internal pressure.

The obtained equations can be reduced to the following one

$$D \left(1 + \frac{C_{12} + RN}{RK_1 - C_{12}} \right) w'''' + \frac{C_{12}}{R} \left(2 - \frac{C_{12}}{RK_1} \right) + N$$

$$+ \frac{BD}{R^2 B_{11} K_1} w'' + \frac{B}{R^2 B_{11}} w = p - \frac{B_{12} N}{B_{11} R} - \frac{D}{K_1} p'' \quad (12)$$

where $N = N_1$ and $B = B_{11} B_{22} - B_{12}^2$. The deflection of the filament-wound shell consisting of helical 36° (with respect to the axis) and hoop plies and having the following parameters

$B_{11}=0.213$ Gpa.m, $B_{12}=0.112$ Gpa.m, $B_{22}=0.56$ Gpa.m, $C_{12}=0$,
 $D=2.55 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Gpa.m³, $K_1 \rightarrow \infty$, $R=0.1$ m, $h_r=4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, $a=18.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m,
 $N=0.5$ pR, $p=4.7$ Mpa is shown in Fig.5. Circles indicate
 experimental results, curve 1 corresponds to the solution of
 Eq.(12), curve 2 represents the linear solution, and curve 3
 illustrates the deflection of the membrane shell, i.e. the
 solution of the following equation

$$w'' - \frac{B}{B_{11}R^2N} w = \frac{B_{12}}{B_{11}R} - \frac{p}{N}$$

which can be obtained from Eq.(12) by setting $C_{12}=D=0$.

CONCLUSION

The simplest first-approximation geometrically nonlinear theory has been developed and applied to analysis of cylindrical shells. It has been shown that nonlinear effects attributed to the changes of shell curvature can be significant in composite shells even if their deflections and slopes are relatively small.

REFERENCES

1. Novozhilov, V.V., Theory of Elasticity, Sudpromghis, Leningrad, 1958, pp. 15-105.
2. Vasil'ev, V.V., Applied Theory of Composite Shells. Mech. Composite Mater., 1985, 5, 843-852.
3. Obraztsov, I.F., Vasil'ev, V.V. and Bunakov, V.A., Optimum Design of Composite Shells of Revolution, Mashinostroeniye, Moscow, 1972, pp. 49-60.
4. Boitnott, R.L., Johnson, E.R. and Starness, J.N., A Nonlinear Analysis of Infinitely Long Graphite-epoxy Cylindrical Panels Loaded with Internal Pressure. 26-th Struct., Struct. Dyn. and Mater. Conf., Orlando, Fla, Apr. 15-17, 1985, Pt.1 Coll. Tech. Pap., New York, 1985, 593-604.